

THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATION IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS

Akhmadov Saydiolim

Student of Tashkent State University of Economics.

E-mail: saydiolimaxmadov@gmail.com

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"Innovation is the only way to win."[1]

American American businessman Steve Jobs

The purpose of the paper is to study and analyze the role of developing the country's innovative potential to attract foreign investments. The main results of the study are to obtain information that in addition to the innovative environment, ideology, politics, economy and culture of the country, foreign investors often pay attention to intellectual, scientific, technical and technological, financial, legal and entrepreneurial resources, which generally includes into the components of the concept of "innovation potential".

Many researchers from different countries are engaged in studying issues related to the development of innovative development as a factor of attracting effective investments. Not only the researchers, but also the owners of the business entity have given their opinions and facts in their articles about how innovations are at the top of the list in attracting investments. For example, Bakir Lashkari, the director of the famous marketing and audit company - Avimatch, thinks about innovation in his articles entitled "Strategic imperative: the role of innovation in attracting investors for startups and entrepreneurs"[1]. "Innovation shows the company's appearance, easily establishes it as a player with an advantage, and includes the market and sales."

The President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, stated that "The management system in the economy is outdated, effective mechanisms for supporting innovative ideas have not been introduced on time, and it remains a serious problem. "Also, technological backwardness, resource and energy-saving technologies, slow implementation of alternative energy sources are obstacles to economic development" [2].

At this point, it is possible to increase the competitiveness of the national economy and enter the world markets, first of all, at the expense of consistent reform of the economy, ensuring the rapid development of new enterprises and production sectors based on high technologies. In other words, economic competitiveness cannot be achieved without the development of innovation activities. Based on the meaning of the term innovation, it can be said that when any discoveries, new events, services and methods are accepted for

dissemination, then they are recognized by the public. In this case, the introduction of the innovation means the process of using the innovation, and from the moment of acceptance of the innovation for distribution, the new quality becomes an innovation.

There are several indicators that determine the effectiveness of innovation investments of countries. For example, the global innovation index (GII) is an index that analyzes the extent to which innovations are used in countries. According to the final data of this index on the use of innovative investments in Uzbekistan in 2023, it was concluded that Uzbekistan produces less innovative products compared to the level of innovative investments (figure 1). It can be seen that in 2023, Uzbekistan was not able to use its innovative capacity sufficiently. The diagram below shows the relationship between innovation

investment penetration and innovation output.
Figure 1. Dependence on the introduction of innovations and the composition of innovations in Uzbekistan

There are several ways that innovation is important in attracting investment in Uzbekistan:

In Uzbekistan, as in many other countries, innovation plays a crucial role in attracting investments and driving economic growth. Here are several key points highlighting the importance of innovation in attracting investments specifically in Uzbekistan:

Economic Diversification: Uzbekistan has traditionally relied heavily on sectors such as cotton, gold, and natural gas. However, to attract diverse investments and reduce dependency on volatile commodity prices, the country is increasingly focusing on economic diversification. Innovation is key to this diversification process, as it enables the development of new industries, technologies, and services that can attract investments from both domestic and foreign sources.

Improving Competitiveness: In a globalized economy, countries must continuously innovate to remain competitive. Uzbekistan recognizes the importance of enhancing its competitiveness to attract investments and stimulate economic growth. By investing in innovation, such as research and development (R&D), technology adoption, and skills development, Uzbekistan can create a more favorable business environment that appeals to investors seeking opportunities in emerging markets.

Creating an Innovation Ecosystem: Establishing a vibrant innovation ecosystem is essential for attracting investments in Uzbekistan. This involves fostering collaboration between government, academia, research institutions, and the private sector to facilitate knowledge transfer, entrepreneurship, and the commercialization of new ideas. By investing in infrastructure, education, and supportive policies, Uzbekistan can nurture a thriving innovation ecosystem that attracts investments in high-growth sectors such as technology, renewable energy, and advanced manufacturing.

Addressing Socio-Economic Challenges: Innovation can also help address pressing socio-economic challenges in Uzbekistan, such as unemployment, poverty, and social inequality. By promoting innovative solutions in areas such as healthcare, education, agriculture, and infrastructure development, Uzbekistan can create new investment opportunities while simultaneously improving the quality of life for its citizens. Investors are often attracted to markets where there is potential for social impact alongside financial returns.

Attracting Foreign Direct Investment (FDI): Foreign direct investment plays a significant role in driving economic development in Uzbekistan.

Innovative policies aimed at liberalizing the economy, reducing bureaucratic barriers, and improving the business climate can attract foreign investors looking to capitalize on the country's untapped potential. Furthermore, showcasing Uzbekistan's commitment to innovation and technological advancement can instill confidence among foreign investors regarding the country's long-term growth prospects.

In conclusion, the study highlights the indispensable role of fostering innovation in attracting foreign investments, particularly in the context of Uzbekistan's economic development. The paper underscores that foreign investors not only consider the innovative environment but also various factors constituting the country's innovation potential, including intellectual, scientific, technical, financial, legal, and entrepreneurial resources. Moreover, it emphasizes the significance of economic diversification, competitiveness enhancement, creation of a robust innovation ecosystem, addressing socio-economic challenges, and attracting foreign direct investment through innovative policies. The analysis underscores that the effective utilization of innovative investments is essential for Uzbekistan's sustainable economic growth and integration into the global economy. Therefore, policymakers and stakeholders are urged to prioritize innovation-driven strategies to capitalize on the country's potential and pave the way for long-term prosperity and competitiveness on the international stage.

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